

Entrepreneurship, Information and Communication Technology Education for Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

The path to global prosperity, as declared by the world leaders is Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for tackling the problems of rapid destruction of natural resources, environmental pollution and climate change. This paper considered Entrepreneurship, Information and Communication Technology Education by looking at the challenges and opportunities of entrepreneurship education. The objective of this paper is to find out the significance of ICT to entrepreneurship education for sustainable development in Nigeria. The paper, however, discussed the concepts of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship education and entrepreneur with the associated characteristics. The evolution and development of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria were delved into. Entrepreneurship education was discussed in relevance to sustainable development. The interaction with some entrepreneurs in Lagos, Ogun and Oyo States revealed that small scale business entrepreneurs are encouraged by using computer-related machines for their business operation. However, the paper concluded that workforce preparation is being slowed down and that entrepreneurship education, as a functional training, can energise the youths for the changing globalisation features. The usefulness of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to entrepreneurs was discussed. This paper recommended that more entrepreneurs should embrace ICT in order to facilitate the operation of their businesses and that government should provide an enabling entrepreneurial environment where emerging entrepreneurs can thrive and innovate for sustainability.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, ICT Education, Sustainable development

Introduction

Unemployment is an economic condition in which individuals seeking jobs remain un-hired. It seems to be increasing among the youths and is causing a lot of unrest among them. The implication of

unemployment is in the forms of kidnapping, banditry, prostitution, cybercrime among others (Efido and Ogbu, 2020). This issue of unemployment, in the past, had been tackled by subsequent governments. Still, the administration of General Olusegun Obasanjo brought about the implementation of entrepreneurship education as a compulsory course in all tertiary institutions, irrespective of course of study, with the main goal of empowering the undergraduates with skill acquisition as an alternative education. This intention continued after graduation at the orientation camp for three weeks, where the Youth Service Corps members were asked to choose a skill to undergo during the camping period. Entrepreneurship education is a functional education, empowering beneficiaries with knowledge, skills and competence in venture creation.

The dearth of 'paid jobs' in Nigeria triggers off the ingenuity in man to create something new, take a risk, constantly fine-tune his products to meet the demands of consumers and maximise profits to become independent. This innate ability brings about entrepreneurial actions (Ayeni, Olufemi and Adesola, 2018). Entrepreneurship is a process engaged in by a creative individual towards contributing to the growth of the economy while creating wealth for self and causing a change to societal problems.

In Nigeria, the term 'entrepreneurship' describes self-employment, that is, people who employ themselves rather than seeking paid employment from the government or other sources (Ugoani and Ibeenwo, 2015). It is the capacity and willingness to develop, organise and manage a business venture and its risks to make a profit (Afolabi, Kareem, Okunbanjo, Ogunbanjo and Aninkan, 2017). It is, therefore, seen as identifying and evaluating economically viable business opportunities, gathering necessary resources to take advantage of them and initiating appropriate managerial skills to ensure success. It is a creative and innovative response to one's situation by doing a new thing or doing an old thing in a new and spectacular way (Oviame, 2010 in Abari and Ayeni, 2017). Entrepreneurship, as opined by Ekwale (2014), is a process of value creation by combining the necessary resources and skills in certain ways and, in so doing, placing products and services on the market at risk and pursuing a profit, thereby benefiting society. These activities, aligned with entrepreneurship are in form of idea generation, creativity and innovation, identification of opportunities, leadership spirit, financial literacy, consistency and perseverance.

To succeed in an entrepreneurship venture, one must go through entrepreneurship education to gain the right skills, knowledge and attitudes (Efido and Ogbu, 2020). This special education is a learning process that seeks to provide learners with the attitude, knowledge, skills and competent to encourage entrepreneurial success in various schooling from basic to secondary schools through graduate university programmes (Anaele, Amadi and Obed, 2016). The core of entrepreneurship education is turning ideas into action and developing a sense of initiative, making it important and pivotal (Bolaito and Nakazelle, 2017). Creative education embraces conception, actualisation, financing, data collection, career formulation, policy promulgation, staff recruitment and orientation

(Ayeni, Olufemi and Adesola, 2018).

It could be said that the training empowers the beneficiaries with long-life skills that enable them to maximise profits to become independent. Entrepreneurship education plays a key role in developing a business environment by creating new ventures, encouraging entrepreneurial orientation and acquiring business skills (the Republic of Rwanda in Abari and Ayeni, 2017).

The process of entrepreneurship is driven by someone known as an 'entrepreneur'. As such, he/she is the centre of the process and the education.

An entrepreneur sets up a business, taking on financial risks in the hope of profit. This business may be farming, manufacturing, retailing or in the service sector.

This is an independent individual who sees an opportunity, utilises it and bears the risks of uncertainties with the mindset to succeed. That is why Kumar (2011) positions an entrepreneur as an individual who has or operates a business venture where profits and revenues are obtained. Also, Bolton and Thompson (2000) see an entrepreneur as someone who consistently produces and invents a product that has recognisable value to his surroundings and the society at large to meet perceived opportunities. He/she utilises the opportunities of instability, turbulence, and lack and wants to produce something new or modify an existing for-profit motive (Bagby, 2008). An entrepreneur is a person that has some comparative advantages in the decision-making process either because of information or different perception of events or opportunities that persist. It was opined by Oseni (2017) that an entrepreneur is an individual who establishes a new business in the face of risks and uncertainties to achieve profit and growth by recognising opportunities and gathering the necessary resources to capitalise on them.

Aja, Onoh and Igwe (2018) quoted entrepreneurs as gurus of entrepreneurship at the Wharton School who behaved like possessed men and women once they experienced a flash of ideas known as entrepreneurship insight. Examples of entrepreneurs start with those youngsters who use their skills of vocation such as hairdressing, fashion designing, bead making, bag making, stove thread making, event decoration, and catering services to big-time entrepreneurs such as Olsen, who made IBM machines, Bill Gates who developed Microsoft wares, Akanni Okoya Thomas, founder of Eleganza Group of Companies, Aliko Dangote, founder of Dangote Group of Companies and so on. All these people play vital roles as catalysts in the nation's economy. Entrepreneurs are characterised by ingenuity, creativity and innovation.

As laudable as this programme is, it seems the main goal, which is to empower young graduates with skills capable of employability for them, is not fully achieved. This paper is looking at the Evaluation of Entrepreneurship Education Programme vis-à-vis its challenges and opportunities.

Every business is an adventure, hence, the ability and possibility for the venture to succeed or fail depend on the capacity of the entrepreneur to employ his/her positive attributes while retraining their negative attributes effectively. According to Onyido and Duru (2019), entrepreneurs possess characteristics such as self-confidence which can be seen as one of the essential attributes an

entrepreneur must possess. Entrepreneur must believe in his/herself and the project they intend to embark on. Entrepreneurs should be able to see the obstacles or difficulties in achieving their goals as challenges which must be faced squarely and conquered. He/she must maintain high emotional stability in the face of difficulties. Another skill an entrepreneur needs is an ability to take risk. He/she must take strategic decisions before embarking on any project. He/she must be result-oriented and set achievable goal and objectives. He/she needs to show a high level of drive by putting in a serious amount of physical and mental energy. An entrepreneur needs to also have the skill of leadership in order to encourage and guide individuals towards achieving organizational goals and objectives.

Objective of the study

This paper seeks to find out the usefulness of Information and Communication Technology to entrepreneurs for Sustainable Development in Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

Entrepreneurship

The term "Entrepreneurship" was obtained from the French word "*Entreprendre*" which literally means "to undertake". This term suggests that entrepreneurship can be regarded as the practice of engaging in activities that are detailed to identify and exploit opportunities for business and the inherent risk involved (Ahmad and Seymour, 2008). Entrepreneurship is commonly regarded as the process of creating new ideas towards self-reliance. It encompasses using individual abilities, money and other assets to achieve profitability and sustainability of the business venture (Okereke, and Okoroafor, 2011). Entrepreneurship can, thus, be said to be a person's capability and willingness to seek and utilise investment opportunities which gradually grow to a large scale. Developing new ideas to develop existing products and generating new ones is known as innovation. The progression of our social existence resulted from the invention of new technologies and ways of doing things.

According to Schumpeter, an Australian economist, as recorded in Ezuka (2012), the single function of entrepreneurship is innovation, such as in getting new product, applying new production method, exploring new market and establishing new forms of organization.

There is a need to note that wealth is created when such innovation results in new demand. Succinctly, entrepreneurship is a process of value creation by combining the necessary resources and skills in certain ways and, in so doing, placing products and services on the market at risk in pursuance of a profit (Ekwale, 2014).

The environment where an entrepreneur exploits opportunities is rather greater than people with brilliance in isolation. Therefore, the time and space of an entrepreneur is important. The concept of entrepreneurship has been refined from being a personal perspective to a kind of behaviour of an

entrepreneur in his/her ability to initiate ideas, perceive opportunity, turn the available resources to exploits profitably and accept risk in times of uncertainty.

Entrepreneurship is also seen as identifying and evaluating economically viable business opportunities, gathering necessary resources to take advantage of them and initiating appropriate managerial skills to ensure success (Nelson, 2010). It is creative and innovative responses to one's situation by doing a new thing or an old thing in a new spectacular way (Oviame, 2010).

In the Nigerian economy, Alhaji Dangote can be compared to or referred to as an entrepreneur who has revolutionised the Nigerian economic space. Starting from a small business and becoming a large business enterprise, he broke new ground, took the risks and explored the opportunities available to him. He is a wealth creator and an employer of labour in the country.

Evolution and Development of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria

Indegenous Entrepreneurship started when people produced more goods than they needed and as such, they had to exchange those surpluses. Through this exchange of produce, entrepreneurship started. Hence, early entrepreneurship started with trade by barter, exchanging goods for goods before any form of money. The historical evolution started from expansion through innovation and inventions (Nzewi, 2017). The period brought about the perception of entrepreneurs to the identification of opportunities and exploitation of new ideas into inventions which were commercialised and thus improved the standard of living of the citizenry. The dramatic change ushered in the use of automobiles, touch lights, computers, mobile phones and so on.

Modern entrepreneurship began with the entrance of the colonial masters who made Nigerians the middlemen for their wares. In 1700 B.C., the merchants from New Guinea came to Nigeria when our fore-parents exchanged a black volcanic glass used to make hunting arrowheads for other goods (Buame, 1996). In this way, modern entrepreneurship emerged. Nigerians started buying and selling on a small scale and later grew to a large-scale business. Presently, there are diversified businesses in production, technologically induced and supported businesses such as assembly plants of vehicles, information technology communication outfits and so on. This is how entrepreneurship thrived and many Nigerians were making profits from buying and selling, hence, becoming recognised traders. The inability of the government to employ most school leavers and the encouragement to go into a private business through the introduction of entrepreneurship education into the curriculum of tertiary institutions and the vocational programme in Basic and Post-Basic Schools, have made the entrepreneurial mindset of the beneficiaries to be quickened.

Entrepreneurship Education in Perspective

The seeming initial absence of entrepreneurship education has brought Nigeria to where it is today: the unemployment of her youths, especially young graduates. This is partly a result of the ignorance of

parents and the community of the usefulness of vocational and technical skills (Okocha, 2009). There is a need to balance the three domains of learning, which are cognitive, affective and psychomotor, to have a complete education and sustainable development.

Hence, the government should provide skills that have been transformed into entrepreneurship education by including them in the curriculum from the Middle Basic Class to tertiary institutions. The NYSC Scheme has also created a space for skills acquisition programmes during the orientation weeks. There is now a significant difference in the lives of learners that participated in skills acquisition programmes and those who did not. The Director General, Sulaiman Kazaure, said at the NYSC Permanent Orientation camp that NYSC has produced successful entrepreneurs through its Skills Acquisition Entrepreneurship Development (SAED) programme. For instance, an NYSC graduate that learnt the skill of sweater weaving ended up translating such skill into a registered business venture which she is prospering on now.

Entrepreneurship and Technology

Entrepreneurship is the creative and innovative industrial skill which brings into existence what was previously available and improvement on the existing ones. The impact of technology on daily life has grown tremendously over the years. It has helped connect the worlds around and acts as a portal to greater knowledge, whether, through the use of laptops, cell phones or any other electronic devices (Garba, 2010). Technology is a must for an entrepreneur to facilitate business operations. Gek (2014) regarded technology as a practical way to meet and satisfy human needs and comforts. The word 'technology' can also be called a collection of techniques. It is the current state of humanity's knowledge of combining resources to produce desired products to solve problems, fulfil needs or satisfy wants. It includes technical methods, skills, processes, techniques, tools and raw materials (Omoriode, Igbunu, Uhwubetine and Obenebe, 2019). However, the importance of entrepreneurship education cannot be overemphasised. They are diligently highlighted below:

- (a) Promotion of creative thinkers who creates something out of nothing and attracts others to identify spheres of opportunities.
- (b) Entrepreneurs develop new markets by introducing new and improved products, services and technology.
- (c) Entrepreneurs promote innovation through involvement in research and developing new innovation, which opens the door to new ventures, markets, products and technology.
- (d) Entrepreneurs reduce dependency on old and obsolete methods, systems, culture and technology. They are the pioneers of bringing new technologies and systems that bring about changes because entrepreneurs are change agents and problem solvers. The mandate initiative is at the social change, which is creating a transformational environment in pursuance of

innovative solutions to the country's most pressing problems that boosts diversification and sustainable economic development.

- (e) Entrepreneurial activities bring about an increase in taxation that boost the savings and earnings of the government, enabling the provision of basic amenities such as road, rail, and housing for the populace.

The Roles of Technology in Entrepreneurship

Technology in Entrepreneurship is a process whereby entrepreneurs use resources and technology systems through collaborative exploration to pursue profit opportunities. This helps increase entrepreneurs' intention and motivation to establish and manage sustainable new venture development. Technology which entails Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), is a vital factor in economic development and social change which makes for continuous innovation and commercialisation of the process by entrepreneurs.

ICT includes all digital technology that assists entrepreneurs in using information and internet facilities. It covers all electronic products that deal with information in a digital form. ICT, therefore, is all digital storage, retrieval and transmission. It makes business more efficient, effective and promptly responds to customers' needs. An entrepreneur cannot do without ICT, especially in this digital information age. It assists business activities, including design, manufacturing, research and development, marketing and feedback.

ICT can effectively and efficiently handle The promotion and urbanisation that has been the norm of the 21st Century with its challenges for economic development. The following are the basic importance of ICT to entrepreneurship:

- (i) better work efficiency and data tracking.
- (ii) greater accessibility and collaboration through cloud computing.
- (iii) consistent software upgrades.
- (iv) data safety, cyber security and important data backups in case of physical damage.
- (v) greater ease of access and customer satisfaction.
- (vi) timely, better and cheaper access to knowledge and information.
- (vii) provision of opportunities for human beings to interact with one another in new and easiest ways.
- (viii) it reduces distance issues in transactions and dealings.
- (ix) ICT offers learning opportunities.
- (x) ICT helps to develop and enhance communication and social networks.
- (xi) It is cost-effective in the sense that it gives way for more effective budgeting.
- (xii) It creates new job opportunities.

- (xiii) It broadens the reach of technologies such as high-speed internet, mobile broadband and computing.
- (xiv) It helps to generate the maximum possible productivity.
- (xv) ICT provides quick access to affordable and better means of communication, leading to an entrepreneur's productivity and profit ability.

Education is the most powerful weapon to change the world (Mandela, 2003). Entrepreneurship education, therefore, is the sound and functional education that serves as the most powerful weapon to change the world in view of all its embedded opportunities.

To access the opportunities of entrepreneurship education, the entrepreneur must be enterprising. The virtues such as being energetic and acquiring the skills of achievement orientation, efficiency, effectiveness, resourcefulness, innovation, an ability to take a risk, plan ahead, engagement in skilful activities and consistency with perseverance must be inherent in the entrepreneur of high repute. Entrepreneurship education opportunities include but are not limited to new market opportunities such as affiliate marketing, distributorship, franchising, technology opportunity, niche opportunity, business opportunities from home such as web design, freelance writing, online business opportunity such as drop shipping, digital marketing, content creation; licensing, competitive opportunity, business to business, electronic commerce, business to customers, mobile businesses, online education or electronic learning business.

Advantages of Entrepreneurship Education

The followings are the advantages of entrepreneurship education:

1. Increased productivity through innovation.
2. Venture creation ability is on the increase.
3. More youths are involved in the creation of small-scale businesses.
4. Enhancement of the transfer of technology-based knowledge.
5. Reduction in the craving for a paid job.
6. Increase in the exportation rate of indigenous products.
7. International revenue is on the increase.
8. Migration of youths from rural areas is reduced.
9. An influx of venture creation brings about a reduction in the prices of goods and services.
10. Increase in the level of the dignity of labour.
11. Reduction in poverty level.
12. Reduction in negative behaviours in the society.
13. Enhancement of sustainable economic development.
14. Improvement in standard of living.

There are many business opportunities worldwide, specifically in Nigeria, based on diverse markets and demographics. However, one must identify the business opportunity suitable for the desired intention. Some ways of identifying business opportunities include environmental scanning, SWOT Analysis, innovation brainstorming, market research, social listening and monitoring.

Despite all the opportunities available in implementing entrepreneurship education, many challenges constrained the implementation of sustainable development. They include corruption, insecurity, road networks, epileptic power supply, inadequate water supply, inaccessible communication networks and support systems for entrepreneurs, manpower problems, financial barriers, illiteracy, poor planning control, competition issues, political instability and many more challenges.

ICT and Entrepreneurship Development

ICT is a diverse set of technological tools and resources used to transmit, store, create, share or exchange information. These technological tools and resources include computers, the internet (websites, blogs and emails), live broadcasting technologies (radio, television and webcasting), recorded broadcasting technologies (podcasting, audio and video players and storage devices) and telephony (fixed or mobile, satellite, video-conferencing, among others UNESCO Portal). Entrepreneurship development enhances entrepreneurial skills and knowledge through structured training and institution-building programmes. It aims to enlarge the base of entrepreneurs to speed up the pace at which new ventures are created.

The emergence of digital knowledge and its application has boosted and is still boosting business. This is why a successful entrepreneur cannot do without ICT in this 21st Century, as it is a strong tool for sustainable development. ICT helps an entrepreneur save costs, enhance administrative effectiveness, promote increased productivity, allow operation across borders, and enable him or her to follow trending issues, culminating in his or her ability to satisfy customers and hence, breaking even in his business for bottom-line achievements. ICT also motivates an entrepreneur to be technologically inclined with a mindset of widening his or her scope by building capacity to generate more employment opportunities, thereby solving unemployment problems and promoting sustainable development in Nigeria.

Sustainable Development

Development is a process that brings about growth, progress, and a positive change from physical, economic, environmental, social and demographic components. This study is all-encompassing because it is about the people and the country in its entirety.

Sustainable development is economic development that is conducted without depletion of natural resources. Hence, it is an organising principle for meeting human development goals while also sustaining the ability of natural systems to provide the natural resources and ecosystem services on which the economy and society depend. The desired result is a state of society where living conditions

and resources are used to meet human needs without undermining the integrity and stability of the natural system. It is meeting the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs in Brundtland Report WCED, 1987 and referenced in University of Cambridge, 2005; Obadimu, 2022.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a collection of 17 interlinked global goals designed to be a "shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and planet, now and into the future"). The SDGs were set up in 2015 by the United Nations General Assembly (UN-GA) and are intended to be achieved by 2030. They are included in UN-GA Resolution called the 2030 Agenda the SDGs were developed in the Post-2015 Development Agenda as the future global development framework to succeed the Millennium Development Goals which were ended in 2015. The SDGs emphasise sustainable development's interconnected environmental, social and economic aspects by putting sustainability at their centre.

The 17 SDGs are: No poverty, Zero hunger, Good health and well-being, Quality education, Gender equality, Clean water and sanitation, Affordable and clean energy, Decent Work and Economic Growth, Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Reduced inequality, Sustainable Cities and Communities, Responsible Consumption and Production, Climate Action, Life Below Water, Life on Land, Peace and Justice Strong Institutions: Partnerships for the Goals

Source: (Obadimu, Clement, 2022)

Though the goals are broad and interdependent, two years later (6th July 2017), the SDGs were made more "actionable" by a UN Resolution adopted by the General Assembly. The resolution identifies specific targets for each goal and indicators used to measure progress toward each target. The year by which the target is meant to be achieved is usually between 2020 and 2030. For some of the targets, no end date is given.

Education for Sustainable Development

Education for sustainable development (ESD) is a term used by the United Nations. It is defined as education that encourages changes in knowledge, skills, values and attitudes to enable a more sustainable and just society for all. ESD aims to empower and equip current and future generations to meet their needs using a balanced and integrated approach to the economic, social and environmental dimensions of sustainable development. In this study, entrepreneurship education is the education for sustainable development because it has the features mentioned above. Entrepreneurship education can empower the current and future generations with profitability and societal values, aligning with Sustainable Development Goal Four (SDG4), quality education that promotes lifelong learning opportunities for all.

Thus, the goal of wealth creation, poverty reduction and value orientation can only be attained and sustained through an efficient education system which impacts learners the relevant skills, knowledge capacities, attitudes and values, which is entrepreneurship education (Agi and Yellowe,

2013). President Muhammadu Buhari, during one of his campaigns in 2015, said that the answers to Nigeria's problems are beyond them and that they are in the hearts and minds of the entrepreneurs.

Conclusion

The paper has highlighted the inherent problems in the nation, among which is the unemployment of our young graduates. It is apparent that the country is slowing down the preparation of the workforce, which are majorly the youths for changing globalisation. Sustainable global economic development is known to be anchored on strong entrepreneurship and ICT education, which most developed countries have keyed into, and Nigeria cannot do less.

Recommendations

The paper, however, recommended the following for effective and efficient entrepreneurship education with entrepreneurial orientation for ventures creation that will lead to sustainable economic development:

1. The entrepreneurship education curriculum should be relevant to global standard's practice.
2. The government should provide a relevant support system for entrepreneurs to encourage their continuing emergence and performance.
3. Government should provide infrastructure, social amenities, friendly and enduring policies and educational platforms that promote entrepreneurship and empower the citizens.
4. Government should create suitable conditions for new businesses to start and thrive while enabling the existing firms to grow by developing new products and services in new markets through appropriate tax policies, supportive physical infrastructure, providing training and information, and promoting incubation and development facilities.
5. Government policies must be structured to nurture an entrepreneurial environment and allow effective opportunities for growth towards sustainable national economic development.
6. Since small and medium-scale industries account for major employability globally, Nigerian governmental policies should protect and preserve emerging entrepreneurs for continuity.
7. ICT should be included in the curriculum of entrepreneurship education to enhance its relevance to global best practices.
8. More small scale entrepreneurs should start using ICT for their business operations.

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